

Guidance Needs of Nursing Students in Iloilo City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Nursing students face numerous stresses and challenges that pose a threat to their well-being. They require guidance to attain satisfactory adjustment in all aspects of daily life in this critical stage of their development. This study was conducted to determine the guidance needs of nursing students in selected schools in Iloilo City. The sample of this descriptive, comparative study consisted of 283 randomly selected students from four nursing schools in Iloilo City. The Guidance Needs Inventory for Nursing Students (GNINS) developed by the researchers was used to gather data. Frequency, mean, standard deviation, and rank were used to describe the data. Independent Samples t-Test and ANOVA set at 0.05 alpha were employed to find out significant difference between variables. The study revealed that nursing students need guidance to a moderate extent. They need more guidance on the aspects of career and academic. Further, results indicated no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to sex, gender, year level, residence, type of school, living arrangement, employment status of parents, monthly family income, number of siblings, birth order and type of family. Guidance remains to be an integral part of nursing education. Continued provision of guidance that is responsive and relevant to the needs of nursing student cohort is therefore necessary.

Keywords: guidance needs, needs inventory, needs assessment, nursing students

INTRODUCTION

Education is considered by Filipinos as a goal that one must achieve or acquire to live a successful life in the future. An individual can gain knowledge, develop skills and attitude that will shape one to a better version of himself. However, as one student moves from a higher level year by year, student life is getting more complex.

Pariat, Rynjah & Kharjana (2014) stated that college students encounter many challenges that can pose threats to their mental health, emotional well-being and performance in school. The transition that is lived up by them can predispose to anxieties and other adversities that can alter the coping mechanism of students especially with regards to their studies. Adjustments then are made in order for them to deal with everyday life. According to Fernandez-Distajo (2013), a college student in the Philippines is expected to have greater independence in thought and action and many would like to be treated as an adult, yet unprepared to assume the role. In fact, many students feel lost in college. Some students even express that they receive no direction and encouragement from others and that some teachers are indifferent to their adjustment difficulties.

Studies have shown that college students face a lot of stressors that some would consider college life to be frustrating and stressful. School requirements and academic pressure, family and social relationships, psychological and emotional concerns, finances, planning for future career, and adaption to new environment are some that trouble them (Oh, Blondin, Cochran, & Williams, 2011; Pariat, Rynjah, & Kharjana, 2014; Baskar, 2015).

In nursing education, stress is acknowledged as one of the most important issues in the contemporary time. Studies indicated that nursing students experience moderate to severe levels of stress and are more prone to stress than other students (Labrague, 2013; Shrestha & Lama, 2015; Abasimi, Atindanbila, Mahamah, & Gai, 2015; Jimenez, Navia-Osorio & Diaz (2010); Seyedfatemi, Tayfreshi & Hagani (2007). Pryjmachuk and Richards (2007) found that stress in nursing students arises from a combination of personal and extracurricular factors rather than from the educational program itself. Meanwhile, Seyedfatemi, Tafreshi & Hagani (2007) reported that the most stressful situations are new friends and working with people they do not know. In a study conducted by Labrague (2013), the most common sources of stress identified by students and faculty include academic demands such as assignments and examinations and balancing academic and clinical work. Clinical sources of stress include inadequate knowledge towards the diagnosis, insufficient skills in doing clinical procedures, unfamiliar and new environment that predispose them to commit mistakes and could lead to patient's death. Other reported sources of stress include poor communication and interaction skills towards clinical instructors, staff and even to physicians. Similarly, Liu, Gu, Wong, Luo & Chan (2015) disclosed clinical, education, confidence, finance and time dimensions as sources of stress. Furthermore, Abasimi, Atindanbila, Mahamah & Gai (2015) found higher personal stressors, academic stressors social stressors among nursing students.

In light of the struggles faced by college and nursing students, guidance is needed to help the students to achieve and properly adjust in various life situations whether in personal, social, academic and career areas. Guidance and counseling service is necessary to help students deal effectively with the formal developmental tasks of adolescent life situation. The unique problems of youth direct to the necessity for counseling services (Prabu, 2015). Without proper guidance, the students would not be able to function properly may it be physically, emotionally, mentally, and socially. This often leads to confusion, wrong decisions, maladjustments and maladaptive behavior (Prabu, 2015).

In the United States, the American School Counseling Association (ASCA) Model (2005) suggests a national framework for a Comprehensive School Counseling Program which has been adapted locally by some educational institutions. The ASCA model incorporates four elements: foundation, delivery system, management systems, and accountability. Foundation provides three student developmental domains which include: academics, career, and personal social/domain (ASCA, 2005). The framework serves to identify guidance needs of which every student must know and accomplish. Grewal (1982) on the other hand identified five areas for guidance: physical, social, psychological, educational and vocational. In the local setting, Villar (2007) reported self-development, studies, social relationships, family and career development as areas that require needs assessment for guidance.

While there are several studies conducted on guidance needs assessment, unfortunately, such were mostly among grade school and high school students. This is possibly because these individuals are denser and inexperienced towards dealing with the

daily challenges in life. They often tend to seek help from their parents, teachers, friends and other relatives or to anyone whom they can find comfort.

In the Philippines, only a few published studies explored the guidance needs of college students and none particularly among nursing students. Since stressors are inevitable, and recognizing the importance of guidance in this critical period of development of nursing students, thus this study was conducted to assess the guidance needs of nursing students in selected schools in Iloilo City. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of guidance needs of nursing students as an entire group and in terms of a) personal needs, b) family needs, c) physical needs, d) social needs, e) academic needs, and f) career needs?
2. Which aspects do nursing students need guidance most?
3. Which aspects do nursing students need guidance least?
4. Are there significant differences in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to a) sex, b) gender, c) year level, d) type of school, e) residence, f) living arrangement, g) employment status of parents, h) monthly family income, i) number of siblings, j) birth order and k) type of family?

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A descriptive, comparative research using one-shot survey design was employed to provide an accurate picture of the nursing students' needs. The participants for this study were chosen using proportionate stratified random sampling technique from four (4) nursing schools in Iloilo City. The data for this study were collected using a researcher-made, self-administered questionnaire titled Guidance Needs Inventory for Nursing Students (GNINS). The items on the questionnaire were adapted from relevant literature primarily from Grewal's (1982) Guidance Needs Inventory, Villar (2007) and Sculli's (2011) Needs Assessment Survey, the guidance form of the West Visayas State University, and questions formulated by the researchers. The instrument was composed of two (2) parts. The first part of the questionnaire includes the personal information of the participants. The second part consists of 47 items with a five-point Likert scale ranging from not needed to very highly needed and was utilized to determine the extent of nursing students' needs in six aspects of concern, namely: personal, family, physical, social, academic, and career. The higher the score, the greater the assumed need for guidance of nursing students.

The instrument was submitted for face and content validation to a panel of five (5) jurors which was composed of a research expert in the field of psychology, guidance and counseling, a university registered guidance counselor, a registered guidance counselor and psychometrician, the president of the Philippine Guidance and Counseling Association Iloilo Chapter, and a registered nurse serving as a guidance counselor in the college of nursing. Consultation was done with a statistician regarding the number and distribution of participants, the sampling technique, scale of means, adequacy of the number of items for each dimension, and statistical tools used.

The instrument was then pilot tested among 30 nursing students with 10 students each year level to detect weaknesses or errors in the instrument and simulate the procedures and protocols that have been designated for data collection. The data collected during the pilot testing were processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences

(SPSS) version 20.0 and the instrument obtained a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.984.

After finalizing the study instrument, permission to conduct the study was secured from the four (4) Deans of the College of Nursing included in the study. The data were collected between July to September 2016. The objectives of the study were explained and informed consent was obtained prior to the administration of the questionnaires. Participants were given ample time to accomplish the questionnaires. The questionnaires were then reviewed for completeness immediately after each data gathering. The researchers tabulated and processed the data gathered using the SPSS version 20.0.

Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and rank were employed to describe the data. t-Test for Independent Samples was used to find out if there is a significant difference in the guidance needs grouped according to sex, gender, type of school, and residence while One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to find out significant difference in the guidance needs grouped according to year level, living arrangement, monthly family income, employment status of parents, birth order, number of siblings, and type of family.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Guidance needs of nursing students as an entire group and in the six aspects*

Guidance Needs	Mean	SD	Description	Rank
Overall	2.88	.884	Moderate Guidance Need	
Career (CAR)	3.11	1.064	Moderate Guidance Need	1
Academic (ACA)	3.05	1.005	Moderate Guidance Need	2
Personal/Psychological (PER)	2.97	.933	Moderate Guidance Need	3
Family (FAM)	2.79	1.004	Moderate Guidance Need	4
Physical (PHY)	2.70	1.015	Moderate Guidance Need	5
Social (SOC)	2.60	1.012	Moderate Guidance Need	6

Legend: Low = 1.00-2.33; Moderate = 2.34-3.66; High = 3.67-5.00

Table 1 shows that nursing students in selected schools in Iloilo City had "moderate guidance needs" (M=2.88; SD=.884) when taken as an entire group. In addition, nursing students had "moderate guidance needs" in the aspects of personal (M=2.97; SD=.993), family (M=2.79; SD=1.004), physical (M=2.70; SD=1.015), social (M=2.60; SD=1.012), academic (M=3.05; SD=1.005) and career (M=3.11; SD=1.064) with career and academic having the highest guidance need mean score.

Table 2. Top guidance needs of nursing students

Guidance Needs	Mean	SD	Description	Rank
a. To possess effective job hunting skills (CAR)	3.27	1.156	Moderate Guidance Need	1.5
b. To improve my study skills and habits (ACA)	3.27	1.178	Moderate Guidance Need	1.5
c. To learn how to spend money more wisely (PER)	3.21	1.278	Moderate Guidance Need	3
d. To develop my test taking skills (ACA)	3.19	1.130	Moderate Guidance Need	4
e. To explore ways on how to make myself competent in my chosen career (CAR)	3.16	1.214	Moderate Guidance Need	5.5
f. To learn how to ask help from teachers concerning lessons I cannot understand (ACA)	3.16	1.073	Moderate Guidance Need	5.5

Table 2 shows that number one guidance needs of nursing students based on their mean scores were possessing effective job hunting skills (M=3.27; SD=1.156) and improving study skills and habits (M=3.27; SD=1.178). This is followed by learning how to spend money more wisely (M=3.21; SD= 1.278), developing test taking skills (M=3.19; SD=1.130), exploring ways on how to make themselves competent in their chosen career (M=3.16; SD=1.214) and learning how to ask help from teachers concerning lessons they cannot understand (M=3.16; SD=1.073).

Table 3. Least guidance needs of nursing students

Guidance Needs	Mean	SD	Description	Rank
a. To understand the physical ill effects of illegal drugs, alcohol and cigarettes (PHY)	2.29	1.302	Low Guidance Need	1
b. To improve grooming and physical appearance (PHY)	2.37	1.252	Low Guidance Need	2
c. To be able to get along better with classmates (SOC)	2.52	1.189	Moderate Guidance Need	3
d. To understand the changing roles of men and women in today's society (SOC)	2.54	1.167	Moderate Guidance Need	4
e. To know the importance of seeking medical treatment when needed (PHY)	2.55	1.223	Moderate Guidance Need	5.5
f. To know the Do's and Don'ts in dating and boy-girl relationship (SOC)	2.55	1.266	Moderate Guidance Need	5.5

As shown in Table 3, nursing students need least guidance in understanding the physical ill effects of illegal drugs, alcohol and cigarettes (M=2.29; SD=1.302). This is followed by improving grooming and physical appearance (M=2.37; SD=1.252), getting along better with classmates (M=2.52; SD=1.189), understanding the changing roles of men and women in today's society (M=2.54; SD=1.167), knowing the importance of seeking medical treatment when needed (M=2.55; SD=1.223) and knowing the Do's and Don'ts in dating and boy-girl relationship (M=2.55; SD=1.266).

Table 4. *t-Test for Independent samples results for difference in guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to sex, gender, type of school and residence*

Categories	M	SD	df	t- value	2-tail sig.
<i>Sex</i>					
Male	2.88	.971	281	.151	.880
Female	2.86	.862			
<i>Gender</i>					
Straight	2.87	.893	281	.489	.625
LGB	2.76	.734			
<i>Type of School</i>					
Public	2.80	.826	281	-1.325	.186
Private	2.94	.937			
<i>Residence</i>					
Urban	2.87	.859	281	.109	.914
Rural	2.86	.929			

not significant if $p > 0.05$

Table 4 shows that male nursing students (M=2.88; SD=.971) have almost the same need for guidance as their female counterparts (M=2.86; SD=.862) when mean scores were compared. The results of the t-test for Independent samples revealed that there was no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to sex, (t=0.151; $p>0.05$). This implies that both sexes have the same concerns regarding the different dimensions of guidance.

Straight nursing students (M=2.87; SD=.893) have higher mean guidance need score when compared to members of LGB nursing students (M=2.76; SD=.734). Statistical analysis however revealed no significant difference in guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to gender (t=0.489; $p>0.05$) based on the t-test for Independent samples result.

The result of the t-Test for independent samples in Table 4 also shows no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to type of school (t = , -1.325, $p>0.05$). Nursing students in public schools (M=2.80; SD=.826) had lower mean guidance score than nursing students in private schools (M=2.94; .937). Statistically, this did not reach a significant level at 0.05.

In terms of residence, t-test for independent samples result revealed that there was no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to residence, (t=.109; $p>0.05$). Those who are living in urban residences (M=2.87; SD=.859) have the same need for guidance as those nursing students living in rural residences (M=2.86; SD=.929).

Table 5. *ANOVA results for difference in guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to year level*

Categories	M	SD	df	F- value	2-tail sig.
<i>Year Level</i>					
Level II	2.97	.817	2	2.964	.053
Level III	2.94	.838			
Level IV	2.69	.970			

<i>Living Arrangement</i>					
Staying in own house	2.84	.866			
Staying in boarding house	2.90	.910	3	1.015	.387
Staying with relatives	2.89	.886			
<i>Employment Status of Mother</i>					
Deceased	2.99	1.170			
Employed	2.86	.881	2	.093	.911
Unemployed	2.87	.816			
<i>Employment Status of Father</i>					
Deceased	2.97	.905			
Employed	2.86	.913	2	.123	.885
Unemployed	2.87	.816			
<i>Monthly Family Income</i>					
Php 30,000 and below	2.89	.829			
Php 30,001 – 60,000	2.81	.896			
Php 60,001 – 90,000	3.08	.923	2	.711	.546
Php 90,001 and above	2.78	1.033			
<i>Number of Siblings</i>					
None	2.73	.904			
1 to 2	2.85	.785			
3 to 4	2.89	.923	3	.569	.636
5 or more	3.05	1.216			
<i>Birth Order</i>					
Only child	2.73	.904			
Eldest child	2.84	.831			
Middle child	2.90	.937	3	.401	.752
Youngest child	2.93	.869			
<i>Type of Family</i>					
Nuclear	2.90	.892			
Extended	2.67	.777			
Single Parent	3.01	.996	3	1.809	.146
Others	3.39	1.169			

not significant if $p > 0.05$

The mean guidance score of nursing students decreases as they move to a higher level (M=2.96, M=2.94, M=2.64 for level II, III and IV respectively). ANOVA result in Table 5 however revealed no significant difference existed in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to year level, (F=0.053; $p > 0.05$).

In terms of living arrangement, those who were staying in the dormitory, boarding house or renting a house (M=2.90; SD=.910) and staying with their relatives (M=2.89; SD=) have higher mean guidance score compared to those who were staying in their own house (M=2.84; SD=.866). Statistically, there is no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to living arrangement (F=1.015, $p > 0.05$).

When grouped according to employment status of parents, those whose mother is deceased (M=2.99; SD=1.170) have higher mean guidance need score when compared to

those with employed ($M=2.86$; $SD=.881$) and unemployed ($M=2.88$; $SD=.876$) mothers. Similarly, those whose father is deceased ($M=2.97$; $SD=.905$) have higher mean guidance needs when compared to employed ($M=2.86$; $SD=.913$) and unemployed ($M=2.87$; $SD=.816$). ANOVA results however revealed no significant difference existed in the guidance needs of nursing students when classified according to mother's employment status ($F=0.093$, $p>0.05$) and employment status of father ($F=0.123$, $p>0.05$).

In terms of monthly family income, those with monthly family income of Php 60,001 to Php 90,000 ($M=3.08$; $SD=.923$) had higher mean guidance need score as compared to those with below Php 30,000 ($M=2.89$; $SD=.829$) and Php 30,001 to Php 60,000 ($M=2.81$; $SD=.896$). Those who belong to a monthly income of Php 90,001 and above ($M=2.78$; $SD=1.033$) have the lowest mean score of guidance needs. ANOVA results show that there is no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to monthly family income ($F=0.629$, $p>0.05$).

As to number of siblings, those who have 5 or more siblings ($M=3.05$; $SD=1.216$) have higher mean guidance need score than those who have no siblings, ($M=2.73$; $SD=.904$), 1 to 2 siblings ($M=2.85$; $SD=.785$), and 3 to 4 ($M=2.89$; $SD=1.216$). As to birth order, nursing students who are the youngest ($M=2.93$; $SD=.869$) in the family have higher mean guidance need score than those who are only child ($M=2.73$; $SD=.904$), eldest child ($M=2.84$; $SD=.831$) and middle child ($M=2.90$; $SD=.937$). ANOVA result in the Table 10 shows that no significant differences exist in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to number of siblings ($F=0.569$; $p>0.05$) and birth order ($F=0.401$; $p>0.05$).

According to the type of family, those who do not belong in either nuclear, extended and single parent type of families have higher mean guidance need score ($M=3.39$; $SD=1.169$) when compared to single parent ($M=3.39$; $SD=1.1.69$); nuclear ($M=2.90$; $SD=.892$). Extended type of families has least mean guidance need score. ANOVA revealed that there is no significant difference in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to type of family $F(2,79)=1.809$, $p>0.05$). This means that guidance needs of nursing students do not vary according to type of family.

DISCUSSION

This study found that nursing students need guidance to a moderate extent. Nursing students in selected schools in Iloilo City need guidance and that they require help or support in the six different aspects of guidance. Previous studies disclosed that nursing students perceive moderate to high level of stress (Labrague, 2013; Shrestha & Lama, 2015; Abasimi, Atindanbila, Mahamah & Gai, 2015; Jimenez, Navia-Osorio & Diaz (2010); Seyedfatemi, Tayfreshi & Hagani (2007). Crisan, Pavelea & Ghimbulut (2015) found that college students encounter major barriers in the career decision process. The result of this study justifies the need for guidance resulting from the many stressors encountered by nursing students in their college years. Interestingly, career and academic remain to be a top priority for college nursing students. While nursing students express more need for assistance on their academics and career plans and decisions, lesser guidance is required in some facets of social and physical aspects. This does not differ much to the primary guidance needs of high school students. Sculli (2011) found high school students need guidance most in the career domain with secondary emphasis on the academic domain, and little emphasis in the personal/social domain. The study supports the ASCA Model

Comprehensive School Counseling Program that strongly advocates for identification of academic, career and social needs for students. While the model has been widely used for elementary and high school population, the ASCA model also serves as useful guide or framework for designing the guidance programs of college students.

Contrary to the results of most studies found in the literature, significant differences in the guidance needs of nursing students grouped according to different personal characteristics is not supported in this study. Among male and female nursing students included in this investigation, both sexes have the same needs in the different aspects of guidance. Similarly, Vinutha & Indiramma (2017) and Parhar, Kaur & Kaur (2013) found no significant differences in the guidance needs of adolescent boys and girls and among male and female secondary school students. Contrastingly, Sculli (2011) also found differences in the guidance needs of male and female high school students. In a study conducted by Kacur & Atak (2011) cited in Ulusoy, Varlıklı, Dağ, Sahranç & Turan (2014), male senior secondary school students have more academic, life, economic, health, job acquisition, bad habits, communication with environment, family and society, self-expression and psychological support problems compared to female students. Dogar, Azeem, Majoka, Mehmood & Latif (2011) revealed matriculation level girls had more career choice problems than of emotional nature. In addition, this study found that whether straight, lesbian, gay or bisexual, nursing students have the same moderate level of guidance needs. Whilst Fisher, Komosa- Hawkins, Saldaña, Thomas, Hsiao, Rauld & Miller (2008) and Ryan (2001) disclosed that LGBTQ students often face challenges due to social discrimination and were at more risk than the general population for developing academically, socially, and emotionally, it is interesting to note that among nursing students included in this study, guidance needs does not differ significantly among straight and LGB groups.

Few published literature is available regarding the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to type of school. In the context of this study, nursing students in public and private schools have the same concerns regarding the different aspects of guidance included in this study. It can be said that nursing students in Iloilo City have moderate guidance needs whether they belong to private or public nursing school. Furthermore, residence is not a notable factor that would result to variation in the guidance needs of nursing students. No matter where the participant grew up, environmental factor or distance from school is not an issue with regard to provision or requirement of guidance. Conversely, earlier study of Ghamari & Gendavani (2013) revealed higher need for psychological guidance of students from urban areas than students from rural areas. The findings of Brawal (2016) indicates there is a significant difference in the guidance needs of rural and urban secondary school students, educational and vocational needs of rural and urban students. While there is no significant difference in the guidance needs of rural and urban students, rural and urban students towards physical needs, social needs, and psychological needs of secondary school students.

It is noteworthy that in the current study, the guidance needs of students decreases as they enter the next year level, however, no statistical significant difference was found. Conversely, Sculli (2011) found difference in the guidance needs of high school students grouped according to grade level. Kyalo & Chumba (2011) found out that first year students have a higher level of academic adjustment compared to other students in the university. Previous researchers on the other hand found that experienced students perceived more academic stressors than novices (Jimenez, Navia-Osorio & Diaz, 2010). Nevertheless, this study only included Level II, III, and IV students, comparison of freshmen nursing students

to higher level students was not determined which could possibly influence the result of the study.

As to living arrangement, nursing students also showed no differences as to whether they stay in their houses or otherwise. Shakurnia & Khajeali (2016) revealed that at a university of medical sciences in Iran, students living at dorms have expressed more counseling needs. Separation from family after university entrance creates some personal, financial and communication problems that may put students in an unfavorable and vulnerable situation. Student life along with living away from family may impose certain conditions and may create difficulties; hence may feel the need for more consultation services.

There was also no variation in the guidance needs of nursing students when grouped according to employment status of parents. According to Almani, Abro & Mugheri (2012), children of working mothers start dreaming and planning their career, building relationships and families independently. They discover possibilities and chances that can lay the foundation of their own identity under the supervision of their mothers. In addition, Cinamon (2001) found that adolescents with employed fathers attributed higher value to the need for the prospective employment to offer management opportunities than did adolescents of unemployed fathers.

Income is necessary to support the basic needs of family particularly in meeting their physiologic needs. Sending children to school also requires a great deal of finances. Studies cited in Smith (2006), stated that children of higher income families are receiving more of the academic and attitudinal benefits of parental involvement than low-income children. Parhar, Kaur & Kaur (2013) posited that there is a difference in the vocational interests of the socio-economically advantaged and non-advantaged students. In this study, however, regardless of income level, nursing students have the same requirement for guidance.

In terms of whether nursing students have siblings or is the only child in the family, nursing students require the same extent of guidance. Horner, Andrade, Delva, Grogan-Kaylor & Castillo (1998) explained that being the youngest places the adolescent at risk of performing less well compared to older adolescents in their classrooms. One possible reason is that adolescents who are the youngest might be raised in more disadvantaged conditions than adolescents born first, especially in the case of poor families. First born children may benefit not only from more parental attention, but also these children may receive more financial resources that can be allocated to their education. Furthermore, being a younger or youngest child may impact the amount of parental attention, while also not receiving financial support due to the possibility that low-income families may struggle with meeting the basic needs of a larger family. Further, in one study conducted by Downey (2001), it revealed that as the number of children in the family increases, the resources accrued by any one child necessarily decline. Because such resources shape educational opportunity, children with few siblings enjoy greater educational success than those with many siblings.

The guidance need of nursing students is also the same whether the student belongs to a nuclear, extended, single parent and other family types. A study conducted by Ruiz & Silverstein (2007) indicated that close and supportive relationship between grandparents and grandchildren are an important factor of children's emotional well-being and psychological benefits. Shumba & Moyo (2014) concluded that bereaved children experienced a variety of circumstances that impacted both positively and negatively on their schooling and rendered them in need of bereavement counseling. Further, Valentina and Singh (2014) stated that nuclear and joint families have extreme need for physical,

educational and vocational needs and least for psychological guidance and respondents from nuclear and joint families expressed need for vocational guidance on top priority.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Guidance remains to be an integral part of nursing education. Nursing students, regardless of personal characteristics have moderate need for guidance. Due to a great deal of various stressors whether in school, external, and clinical setting, nursing students experience a great load of pressures from time to time with continuous changes in workload while they are in the nursing school. However, nursing students may have developed effective ways of coping with daily life stressors enabling them to still function productively.

While nursing students are nearing adulthood or are in their adult years, they still need help mostly in the area of career and academics. Nursing students are highly concerned about their academic performance and their ability to succeed in their chosen fields in the future. In addition, these students still need assistance in personal, family, physical and social aspects of their lives.

This study recognizes the pivotal role of guidance in nursing education, thus recommends continuous provision of guidance that is responsive and relevant to the needs of the nursing student cohort. Results of this study can lay the foundation for the development of a Comprehensive Guidance Program for nursing students. Guidance program and services should address all the needs of the nursing students giving more emphasis on their primary concerns to promote their holistic development as helping and caring professionals.

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